

STYLISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF OXYMORON AND ITS FUNCTIONS IN LITERARY TEXTS

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Abstract. *The thesis deals with stylistics characteristics of oxymoron as a productive device in the English literature. As the main concept of oxymoron to describe its versatile uses in contexts and to understand how to show this expression on oxymoron expressions in which depicting the multilateral styles in the language through the principles of transformational grammar construction. Furthermore, in discussing or analyzing language communication, readers ought to consider oxymoron as a logical way of how language and stylistic construction are used. In this thesis will show factors of oxymoron which suggesting that in any types of texts utilized differently than literal speech. The characteristics of oxymoron in the viewpoint of “cognitive linguistics” intensify the quality of figure of speech in the literary texts and process of creating further dramatic genres in literature.*

Key words: *cognitive linguistics, factors of oxymoron, depicting features of oxymoron, a set of phrases of language.*

Аннотация. *Бу тезис инглиз бадиий адабиётида ўзининг сермазмундорлиги ва бўёқдорлик ифодаси билан алоҳида ажралиб турувчи услубий қурилмалардан бири оксюморон ва унинг услубий хусусиятлари матн орқали таҳлил қилинади. Оксюморон ўзининг ноодатий боғланиши билан стилистик услубият механизмларининг узвий алоқадорлик самарисини кучайтиради айниқса китобхонлар салоҳиятини чуқур ўйлашга ва изланишга мажбур қилади. Оксиморон ва унинг когнитивлик хусусиятлари адабиёт жанрларида кенг қамровли лингвостилистик меанизм шакллантирувчиси сифатида қаралади.*

Калим сўзлар: *когнитив лингвостилистика, оксюморон хусусиятлари, услубларини таҳлиллаш, тил ибора-йигиндиси.*

The characteristic traits of stylistic devices are Oxymoron, Antithesis, Irony, Paradox which are non – verbal connection in the belles – letters style, serving to depict the language drama and fiction more expressive and create a great work of art and of a great increase of the intensity, image and event – under the influence of events serving to enhance the dyeing as well they may be called “aesthetic-cognitive” or called functional styles of the language.[1]

Actually, connecting two incompatible words serve to form a new meaning result which emerges in literary texts. They investigate language potentialities of making the utterance more effective, paying much attention to the analysis of stylistic means of the language, of their nature and functions, their classification and possible interpretation of the additional meanings they may carry in the sentences. One of the non – logical connections from them is oxymoron which is productive and widely used in literature by authors to intensify linguistic principles of linguistics. Its functions as a means of getting the reader’s attention through the pairing of opposing or contradictory words. Not only reading these words together will often cause a reader to pause and think about what the writer is trying to convey but also give a feeling of pleasure, a

pleasure, which is derived from in which the content is wrought. Since the belles-letters style has a cognitive function as well as an aesthetical one, it follows that it has something in common with scientific style.

“Oxymoron is a Greek word that means two things that do not fit represents a combination of lexical units. Oxymoron is a new concept and creates imaginations.” (А. Квятковский. “Поэтический словарь” стр.181).[2]

Naturally, when words come together, they are classified into word structures such as: *adv + adj*, *adj + noun*, *verb + adv*, *adv+adj+ noun phrase* which intensify the expressive meaning of the language to form main syntactic level of the linguistics. An oxymoron is the interaction between the non-logical and the contextual logical meanings of a word which is based on contradictory two word combinations or phrases.[3]

So the marker of these structures is to identify the modifier of the sentences if its function expresses of cognitive effect in the belles-letters style. For example, for the oxymoron *fiend angelical* the general context indicates that the noun is to be considered Juliet’s objective Judgment and the modifier her subjective Judgment of Romeo. Thus, the movement from noun to modifier indicates a movement from factual to subjective Judgment of Romeo. In this context he is *fiend* for what he has done but to her he is (and she believes he essentially is) *angelical*. The stronger word here is *fiend*, which goes contrary, to her ordinary feelings. The thought is, first, *fiend*, then modified to *angelical*. We use nouns to name what things are, adjectives to describe things as they are seen from a particular point of view. Juliet thinks Romeo is a fiend and tyrant, although she sees him as angelical and beautiful. Had the entire context in which *fiend angelical* appears been quoted, one would see that sometimes the unfavorable evaluation, considered as the objective Judgment, appears as the modifier, and the emotive drama of evaluation, the favorable epithet, as the noun.

Therefore, the order and syntax of the constituents of the oxymora in this particular passage may not matter. It is only general discourse – the context-that can help us interpret these oxymora by differentiating between the modifier and the head in term of subjective versus objective reality.[4] In fiction, oxymorons are positive in image and character serves to reveal its negative qualities, for example, “*It was a terribly goodness from wickedness life for Little Clause.*” (from “Little Clause and Big Clause” by Hans Kristian Andersen.p.7). So the writer uses oxymoron device trying to describe the situation positively *terribly goodness* means to amazingly or surprisingly state for him although his difficulties in life. “The Headless of Horseman” called book is also well known in the world by Mayne Reid (1866) in the ninetieth century of dramatic story.

The horseman had not a head despite of being headless which story based on his actions.

The writer uses the oxymoron device very attractive no one can’t stop to read it, so utilizing like oxymoron devices in literary meaningfully to attract any readers to think it. In summary, the fictional characteristics of oxymorons are compact in size, methodologically, the power of influence is incomparable, from visual means is one. Such a style non- logical but made readers to think cognitively in the language communication increases the effectiveness and consistency, the content of the text humorous – satirical paint description for readers to discuss whether it shows positive phenomenon or not, in other words, it reveals in short, concise lines of genres in the literary texts.

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